

Factors Affecting the Activities of Improving the Quality of Teaching Political Theory Subjects – Research at Universities under the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Vietnam

Dr. Nguyen Thi Thu Thoa
Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry, Vietnam

Abstract:- Improving the quality of training, renovating teaching methods of political theory subjects of universities and colleges in Vietnam is now a necessary requirement, suitable for the training program according to the standards orientation of capacity development of learners, built on the basis of modern educational theories and development trends of educational practice in the 21st century. The article points out some factors affecting the activities of improving the quality of teaching political theory subjects at universities today.

Keywords:- Teaching Methods, Political Theory, Lecturers, Students.

I. MAKE A PROBLEM

Political theory education is an important task in the ideological work of the Party in order to equip learners with knowledge of Marxist-Leninist theory, Ho Chi Minh's thought and the lines of the Communist Party of Vietnam in a fundamental way. systematically, helping learners build worldview and scientific methodology, improve their level of theoretical thinking, improve leadership capacity, political bravery and revolutionary moral qualities. The 10th Congress of the Party determined: "Nurturing students and students who aspire to build a rich and strong country, sticking to the future of the community and the nation, cultivating the bravery, qualities and lifestyle of the young Vietnamese generation" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2009).

President Ho Chi Minh has thoroughly grasped the ideology of cadres studying political theory, Uncle Ho advised: The study of political theory is not to turn comrades into mere theorists, but to how for your work to be better, that is to say, you must learn the spirit of Marxism-Leninism in order to apply those stances, views and methods to better solve practical problems in the world and our revolution (Le Anh Xuan, 2011). Thus, learning theory is essential to apply it in practice. However, in reality, the teaching of political theory subjects in our country is still not effective. Many

lecturers are still using one-way communication methods "teacher reads and students copy", conveying facts that are dry and rigid, leading to students feeling bored with the subject, even some students are bored with the subject. students are afraid of the subject. In Resolution No. 37-NQ/TW "on theoretical work and research orientation up to 2030", it was clearly stated that: "theoretical work has limitations and shortcomings... propaganda, education and training work still exist" political theory training is still limited in quality, duplicated in content and curriculum; slow to innovate on methods..." (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2014).

Vietnam started international integration in 1986, Vietnamese society has had many changes from economy to education. However, the educational goal is always the same: to train people who are both intellectuals and politically conscious (Mai Quoc Dung, 2021).

It can be said that political theory subjects do not directly provide technological solutions, do not directly produce material wealth, do not directly carry out the cause of industrialization and modernization, but directly providing information, fostering patriotism, national pride, scientific worldview, revolutionary life view, building and consolidating students' firm confidence in the views and directions of Party, policies and laws of the State.

II. FACTORS AFFECTING ACTIVITIES TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF TEACHING POLITICAL THEORY

A. *Firstly, the influence of factors related to lecturers in improving the teaching quality of political theory subjects.*

Among the 7 criteria related to lecturers, including 1 to 7 on the Likert scale of 5 levels ("1. Absolutely no influence" to "5. Totally influence") to consider their influence on improving the quality of political theory teaching. Test the reliability as well as the appropriateness of these 8 criteria in the 5-level Likert scale using SPSS software.

Table 1: Influence of factors related to lecturers

Criteria	Influential factors (N=224) (1: Completely unaffected; 2: No effect, 3. Sometimes it doesn't, 4. Very influential, 5: Totally influential)	Level of impact				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Teaching capacity	2,2	23,6	0,9	46,7	26,6
2	Moral qualities	2,6	27,1	10,0	50,2	10,0
3	Pedagogical skills	2,2	2,6	2,2	64,6	28,4
4	Pedagogical style	2,2	3,1	5,7	74,7	14,4
5	Teaching experience	2,6	3,5	2,6	42,8	48,5
6	Psychology, emotions	2,2	3,5	20,5	43,2	30,6
7	Language and communication	3,9	24,5	4,4	57,2	10,0

Source: Survey results on the topic "Improving the quality of teaching major theoretical subjects at universities of the Ministry of Industry and Trade"

Table 1 shows that, out of 7 factors selected to be surveyed, the research team found that there are 5 factors that are assessed by the lecturers and students themselves as having the percentage of influence at the level of "4. Very influential" and "5. Totally influential" is the highest, respectively: factor 5 - "Teaching experience" (91.3%), factor 3 - "Pedagogical skills", 4 - "Pedagogical style" (89) .1%, 6 - "Psychology, emotion" (73.8%) and 1 - "Teaching capacity" (73.3%). In general, there are many factors belonging to the lecturers themselves, which strongly influence the process of improving the quality of political theory teaching in recent years. However, the number of factors considered in Table 1 or 5 factors that have just been selected for analysis is relatively large, not general, not concise in terms of expressive meaning and cannot reflect comprehensively. However, when assessing the influence from the student survey, "teaching capacity" and "teaching experience" are the two factors that have the strongest influence on the process of improving the quality of teaching major theoretical subjects in three universities of the Ministry of Industry and Trade in recent times.

The two groups of factors, namely the group of factors of faculty competence and the group of factors of lecturer experience, have a causal effect on the degree (frequency) of applying traditional and modern teaching methods and techniques (coefficient of adjusted correlation $R = 0.69$) and modern teaching methods and techniques (adjusted correlation coefficient $R = 0.57$) of the teaching staff. This has theoretical implications and guides practice. Because, from here, in order to improve the quality of teaching political theory, two groups of influencing factors are the capacity of lecturers and teaching experience. Of course, statistics show that, in addition to these two groups of factors, there are still other factors, but the two tested factors have a very significant impact (accounting for more than 50%).

➤ When applying regression analysis using SPSS software, we found that:

- The more qualified teaching staff, the better, tend to choose and regularly apply traditional teaching methods and techniques combined with modern ones instead of simply choosing one of the two methods. this formula. To some extent, this result is showing that the teaching staff of these universities have a harmonious, dialectical and appropriate approach in the process of improving the

quality of teaching in the world. both content and methodological aspects. Agreeing with the initial research results showing that not only thinking but also practice, they are not too extreme, biased to choose, apply a single teaching method and technique, but can flexibility, integrating content and methods in a harmonious way brings high efficiency.

- Meanwhile, lecturers with many years of teaching experience tend not to choose nor apply traditional methods and techniques in combination with modern or modern methods and techniques in teaching. teaching political theory. This also means that teachers with seniority and long-term teaching experience seem to mainly use traditional teaching methods and techniques mainly in the teaching process. From here, the solution to the situation is to focus on propaganda and encouragement solutions, encouraging and motivating solutions so that the long-term and experienced lecturers can self-discipline, trying to self-innovate the ways and techniques of teaching Political theory in a more suitable way (it can be a method, a technique of both traditional and modern teaching, or a modern way, technique, ... rather than simply applying traditional teaching methods and techniques, which are no longer appropriate).
- The teaching staff with seniority or not much teaching experience tend to either choose to apply modern teaching methods and techniques, or combine traditional and modern teaching methods. This also means that they do not seem to accept the use of methods and techniques of teaching Political Theory by purely traditional methods and techniques. The explanation for this result can come from many reasons such as age, relatively young age, advantage in the application of information technology in teaching, etc., but in our opinion, to have a more rigorous argument. Should there be other qualitative research results to support?

B. Second, the training program factor affects the improvement of the quality of political theory teaching

To examine the impact of the current group of factors on the current training program on the teaching innovation activities of political theory, the research team has developed 6 criteria (criteria – TC) related to the management of political theory. The Academy's assessment includes TC1 to TC6 on a 5-point Likert scale ("1. Completely no influence" to "5. Totally influential"). Test the reliability as well as the

appropriateness of these 5 criteria in the 5-level Likert scale using SPSS software.

Table 2: Factors of the training program affecting method innovation

Criteria	Influential factors (N=224) (1: Completely unaffected; 2: No effect, 3. Sometimes it doesn't, 4. Very influential, 5: Totally influential)	Level of impact				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	How to design the program	2,7	3,6	23,2	55,8	14,7
2	Quality of the curriculum	22,3	3,1	6,3	51,3	17,0
3	Allocation of overall time, subjects, lessons, etc.	22,3	4,5	10,3	48,7	14,3
4	Form of training (concentrated, unfocused, ...)	1,8	11,2	36,2	43,3	7,6
5	How to test and evaluate learning results	2,7	24,1	6,3	55,4	11,6

Source: Survey results on the topic “Improving the quality of teaching major theoretical subjects at universities of the Ministry of Industry and Trade”

The results shown in Table 2 show a number of notable issues as follows: Firstly, among the 5 established criteria, the opinions of lecturers and students believe that there are 03 criteria of proportionality. Levels 4 and 5 have greatly influenced the process of improving the quality of political theory teaching over the past time. Those are 2 criteria in terms of form, specifically: 1 - How to design the program (70.5%) and TC3 - Allocation of overall time, subjects, lessons... (63.0%) and 01 criteria related to the content of the program is criterion 2 - Quality of the curriculum (68.3%). Next, this result accurately reflects the relationship between form and content, between content innovation, lecture quality and teaching quality improvement. Chapter 1. From here, the research team believes that improving the quality of theory teaching in the coming time needs to be considered in the overall relationship with the renewal of curriculum design and development (number of lessons, number of lessons, and number of lessons). subject, number of periods, ...) or the allocation of teaching time (the overall program, for each

subject, each lesson, ...) to ensure that it is a motivating factor, “supporting” rather than a hindrance program to improve the quality of teaching political theory of lecturers at universities under the Ministry of Industry and Trade in the coming time.

C. Third, the influence of the group of factors related to facilities and equipment to improve the quality of teaching political theory subjects.

Similar to the presentation in the Table 2 groups of factors, the research team has developed 5 criteria related to facilities and equipment of three universities under the Ministry of Industry and Trade, including 5 criteria: on a 5-point Likert scale (“1. Absolutely no influence” to “5. Completely influence”) to consider their influence on the activities of improving the teaching quality of political theory of the University. teaching staff. Test the reliability as well as the appropriateness of these 5 criteria in the 5-level Likert scale using SPSS software.

Table 3: Factors in terms of facilities and equipment affecting teaching quality

Criteria	Influential factors (N=224) (1: Completely unaffected; 2: No effect, 3. Sometimes it doesn't, 4. Very influential, 5: Totally influential)	Level of impact				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Tables and chairs, rooms, computers, projectors, speakers, microphones, ...	2,2	3,6	44,2	43,8	6,3
2	Library system	3,1	5,8	37,9	47,8	5,4
3	System of learning and research documents (print and digital)	3,1	3,1	41,5	45,5	6,7
4	Academic and research space	3,1	3,6	38,4	48,2	6,7
5	Training and reward budget	2,7	8,0	42,9	37,9	8,5

Source: Survey results on the topic “Improving the quality of teaching major theoretical subjects at universities of the Ministry of Industry and Trade”

Table 3 shows that, out of the 5 criteria given to ask the opinions of lecturers and students in 3 universities, the following 4 criteria have the highest rate of Level 4 and 5 evaluation, respectively: TC 4 - Academic and research space (54.9%), TC2 - Library system (53.2%), TC3 - System of study and research documents (print and digital 52.2%) and TC1 - Tables and chairs, rooms, computers, projectors, speakers, microphones... (50.1%). Notably, factors like TC1 were expected by the research team to have the strongest influence on improving teaching quality, but the results were not. To explain this, it can be seen that, over the years, the

Board of Directors has spent a lot of resources and efforts to modernize classrooms, lecture halls and equipment such as projectors, audio, tables and chairs, air conditioners, remodeling the hall, ... in the direction of best serving the teaching and learning process. Thus, the TC1 survey results have a small influence on improving the teaching quality of the teaching staff.

However, in the coming time, universities also need to pay attention, invest in and accelerate the modernization of facilities in a new and more modern direction as the survey

results show in criteria TC3, TC4. That is building a repository of rich, complete, digitized, accessible documents...; Smart libraries, digital libraries, etc. Schools also need to soon implement the project of building smart universities, forming space and many environments, opportunities for exchange and academic exchange between students. with each other and with the faculty, for example, conference rooms, seminars, online rooms; practice rooms, simulation and case-solving rooms for subjects with a learning-practice, learning-applying approach that are used by leading schools and research institutes in public policy training, governance implementation, etc. All these innovations, although difficult, are quite new, but very important. Because, they will significantly support the process of improving the quality of teaching in a modern, scientific, and new direction, approaching the teaching and training trends of students like training institutions advanced at home and abroad.

III. CONCLUSION

Improving the quality of teaching and learning in general, and the teaching and learning of political theory subjects in particular, is a constant issue that has always been of concern and has been discussed a lot in different aspects. Ideological and theoretical work plays an important role in the protection and development of Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's thought, viewpoints and lines of the Communist Party of Vietnam. President Ho Chi Minh once pointed out that when the right thoughts are right, the actions will not be wrong and only the revolutionary tasks will be fulfilled. Therefore, in order to effectively carry out the struggle on the ideological and theoretical fronts, and protect the ideological foundation of the Party, it is necessary to improve the quality and effectiveness of research and study of political theory.

Improve the quality of teaching and learning political theory subjects, but under the conditions of credit-based training and in the spirit of mastering the viewpoint of fundamental and comprehensive innovation in higher education in accordance with Resolution 29-NQ/TW of the 8th Party Central Committee Conference, term XI, is a very urgent matter in the current conditions.

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